

Buckling analysis, design and optimisation of variable stiffness sandwich panels

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Abstract

A rapid semi-analytical model is developed based on the Ritz energy method for the buckling analysis of variable stiffness (VS) sandwich panels. VS is introduced into the structure by allowing the fibre angle of the composite face-sheets to continuously vary in the transverse direction and transverse shear effects are included with a first-order-shear deformation theory with additional shape functions for shear strains. The model is shown to be in good agreement with a commercial finite element package whilst requiring less degrees of freedom. A parametric study revealed that VS sandwich panels with high shear modulus cores, above a threshold value, can achieve similar gains in buckling performance to that observed with thin VS plates. However, below this threshold value, core shear crimping modes can become critical in highly loaded local regions, due to pre-buckling load redistributions, resulting in significantly reduced performance gains compared to straight fibre panels. Results from an optimisation case study show that panels with a core shear stiffness above the threshold required to prevent crimping, can achieve improvements up to 78% compared to straight fibre panels. However, with reducing core shear modulus below the threshold value, the improvement reduces to less than 1% with shear crimping modes dominating.

1 Introduction

Traditional tailoring of fibre reinforced composites is achieved by varying the orientation of fibres through the thickness of a laminate. However, recent advancements of automated fibre placement (AFP) and tape laying technologies has led to the possibility of steering fibres in the plane of a ply thus creating variable stiffness (VS) laminates and significantly increasing the design space available to engineers. In recent times, performance benefits of VS laminates have been shown for the buckling and post-buckling of plates [1–4], shells [5] and stiffened panels [6–8], the stress distribution around discontinuities [9, 10] and stiffness blending of structures [11, 12]. The manufacture of VS laminates has been achieved to date largely through the established AFP [11] and lately through an early concept manufacturing method called continuous tow shearing [13, 14].

The majority of work to date on the buckling of VS structures is limited to simple configurations, such as plates and shells, with simple boundary conditions. Analytical and semi-analytical methods [1, 2, 4], whilst providing an accurate and computationally efficient alternative to finite element analysis (FEA), are often limited to simple cases with more complex scenarios (loading, boundary conditions, geometry) requiring FEA. Recently, Coburn et al. [6, 7] developed an analytical model based on the Ritz energy method for the buckling analysis of stiffened VS panels including a first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT) to enable the study of thick laminate sections. Using the model in a follow-up optimisation study [8], it was shown that stiffened VS panels can achieve mass reductions compared to straight fibre stiffened panels, albeit to a lesser extent than plates considered in isolation [1, 3, 4].

One application of VS that has not been explored is the use of fibre-steering to create VS sandwich panels. Sandwich panels are well known to be efficient structures in bending and buckling and for this reason are commonly used in regions where supported edges are spaced apart. To the best of the authors

Figure 1: VS sandwich panel idealisation as a Mindlin-Reissner plate with loading, dimensions and the global coordinate system shown.

knowledge, the combination of a sandwich panel configuration and VS through fibre-steering has not been explored to date. The aim of this work is to use the approach presented by Coburn et al. [7], including a FSDT in a semi-analytical Ritz model, to explore structural configurations of VS sandwich panels.

The following sections are structured as follows. Section 2 develops a semi-analytical model for the buckling analysis of VS sandwich panels subject to uniaxial and biaxial loading and clamped and simply-supported boundary conditions. A parametric study is then performed in Section 3 on the fibre angle variation for panels with various core properties followed by a discussion of the failure modes and significance of core shear stiffness. In section 4 an optimisation study using various control points is performed identifying optimal configurations and improvements. Finally, the paper is concluded in Section 5.

2 Semi-analytical model

2.1 Sandwich panel description and loading

The formulation considers a sandwich configuration consisting of two identical VS composite face sheets, individually constrained to be balanced and symmetric about their local geometric midplane, either side of a homogeneous orthotropic core material as shown in Figure 1. The sandwich panel is prismatic with the fibre-steering, and consequently stiffness variation, in the transverse (y -direction) of the laminates and is subject to uniaxial and biaxial loading applied as uniform end-shortenings.

2.2 Skin fibre representation

Several definitions for the fibre variation over the plane of a laminate have been proposed in literature ranging from simple linear variations [15] to more complex higher-order variations [4]. Here, the piecewise linear method [16] is used due to its ease of visualisation and immunity to Runge's phenomenon [17]. The variation in the y -direction is given by:

$$\theta(y) = \begin{cases} \theta_{1,2}(y) & \text{if } y_1 \leq y < y_2 \\ \theta_{2,3}(y) & \text{if } y_2 \leq y < y_3 \\ \dots & \\ \theta_{n-1,n}(y) & \text{if } y_{n-1} \leq y < y_n \end{cases} \quad \text{where} \quad \theta_{i,i+1}(y) = \left(\frac{T_i - T_{i+1}}{y_i - y_{i+1}} \right) y + \frac{T_{i+1}y_i - T_i y_{i+1}}{y_i - y_{i+1}}; \quad (1)$$

T_i and T_{i+1} are the fibre orientations at adjacent control points; and y_i and y_{i+1} the y -position of the adjacent control points in the global coordinate system. A VS ply is designated by $\langle T_1 | T_2 | \dots | T_n \rangle$ for n control points whose positions are given by $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$.

2.3 Formulation overview

The three-dimensional sandwich panel is idealised as a plate with transverse shear flexibility as shown in Figure 1. Prior to the buckling analysis, a pre-buckling analysis is required to determine the non-uniform

stress distribution in the VS structure. Both the pre-buckling and buckling analyses are performed using the Ritz energy method, on the total complementary energy and total potential energy respectively. This approach requires formulating the energy of the system, assuming a form of the solution with unknown coefficients, minimising with respect to these coefficients and solving the system of linear equations. The buckling analysis considers a FSDT by including shape functions for transverse shear strains in the xz - and yz -directions in addition to the out-of-plane deflection.

2.4 Stiffness matrices

For sandwich panels consisting of identical face-sheets and a core material the **A**-, **B**-, **D**-stiffness matrices about the global midplane are given by:

$$\mathbf{A} = 2\mathbf{A}_{fs} + \mathbf{A}_c, \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{D} = 2\mathbf{D}_{fs} + \frac{(h_{fs} + h_c)^2}{2}\mathbf{A}_{fs} + \mathbf{D}_c, \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts fs and c indicated a single face-sheet and the core respectively. It is assumed that the core thickness does not change under loading and the face-sheet laminates and core have null **B**-matrix terms about their local midplane. Due to the varying fibre orientation of the face-sheets all stiffness matrix terms are variable in the y -direction. The transverse shear stiffness terms are determined using the approach detailed in Kollár and Springer [18] where the face-sheets are assumed to be thin and have a high transverse shear stiffness compared to the thick core. The shear stress is assumed to be negligible in the face-sheets and constant in the core and the equivalent transverse shear stiffness of the sandwich plate is given by core stiffness properties as:

$$H_{ij} = \frac{(h_{fs} + h_c)^2}{h_c} \bar{Q}_{c,ij}, \quad (3)$$

where $i, j = 4, 5$ and the global coordinate stiffness matrix, $\bar{Q}_{c,ij}$, is determined by applying the transformation matrix to the local coordinate stiffness matrix, \mathbf{Q}_c which for an orthotropic core is given by:

$$\mathbf{Q}_c = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{c,44} & Q_{c,45} \\ Q_{c,54} & Q_{c,55} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{c,44} & C_{c,45} \\ C_{c,54} & C_{c,55} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} G_{c,23} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{c,13} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Full explanations of all stiffness and transformation matrices can be found in Reference [18].

2.5 Pre-buckling

Two pre-buckling load cases are considered, in both cases the transverse edges are subject to a uniform end-shortening of Δx in the x -direction with case A allowing longitudinal edges to expand and case B additionally applying an end-shortening of Δy in the y -direction to create a biaxial stress state as shown in Figure 1. In both cases all edges are free to translate parallel to the edge direction and the panel is constrained to have null A_{i6} ($i = 1, 2$) extension-shear coupling terms resulting in a purely biaxial stress state.

2.5.1 Total complementary energy

The energy of the system for pre-buckling is formulated as the total complementary energy extending the approach of Wu et al. [4] who found that utilising the Ritz method for the pre-buckling problem of VS plates with prescribed edge displacements was intractable with the total potential energy. The total complementary energy of a plate subject to prescribed edge displacements is given by [19]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_c = & \frac{1}{2} \iint_S \left[a_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 + 2a_{12} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} + a_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} \right)^2 + a_{66} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y} \right)^2 \right. \\ & \left. - 2a_{16} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_i}{\partial x \partial y} - 2a_{26} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_i}{\partial x \partial y} \right] dy dx \\ & - \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \Phi_i}{\partial y^2} u - \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y} v \right]_{x=a/2} dy + \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y_i^2} u - \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x_i \partial y_i} v \right]_{x=-a/2} dy \\ & - \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} v - \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y} u \right]_{y=b/2} dx + \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \Phi_i}{\partial x^2} v_i - \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y} u \right]_{y=-b/2} dx, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where a_{ij} ($i, j = 1, 2, 6$) are the terms of the inverse of the in-plane stiffness matrix \mathbf{A} , u and v displacements in the x - and y -directions respectively, S the surface of plate and Φ the Airy's stress function where:

$$N_x = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2}, \quad N_y = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} \quad \text{and} \quad N_{xy} = -\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x \partial y}, \quad (6)$$

and N_x , N_y and N_{xy} are the in-plane stress resultants. The analysis is further simplified and generalised by expressing the total complementary energy in the normalised coordinate system of ξ and η with:

$$\xi = \frac{2x}{a} \quad \text{and} \quad \eta = \frac{2y}{b}. \quad (7)$$

2.5.2 Shape functions

Due to the panel being prismatic (variation only in the y -direction) the N_y stress resultant is constant over the entire domain and can be captured with a single term. By constraining the panel to have no extension-shear coupling or shear loading the N_{xy} stress resultant is null over the entire domain. The only variable stress resultant requiring representation with a series expansion is N_x which varies in the y -direction. The Airy's stress function can therefore be represented as a polynomial series expansion given by:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \eta^2} = \frac{b^2}{4} N_x = \sum_{h=0}^{H-1} [c_h L_h] = c_h L_h \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial \xi^2} = \frac{a^2}{4} N_y = d_0, \quad (8)$$

where L_h is the series in the y -direction, H the number of terms in the L_h series and c_h the unknown coefficients. The variation in the y -direction is free at boundaries and L_h is chosen as a Legendre polynomial series. Legendre polynomials form an orthogonal set over the interval $[-1, 1]$ allowing elimination of terms in the energy integrals creating a sparse banded stiffness matrix and good numerical conditioning properties. The total complementary energy of the system can then be expressed in terms of the unknowns c_h by substituting the shape functions in Equation 8 into the normalised form of Equation 5.

2.5.3 Principle of stationary complementary energy

Applying the principle of stationary complementary energy, $\delta \Pi_c = 0$, which is mathematically identical to the principle of stationary potential energy for linear systems, to the non-dimensional form of the total complementary energy and minimising with respect to the unknown coefficients, c_h , results in a set of linear equations which expressed in matrix form are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_{cc} & \mathbf{U}_{cd} \\ \mathbf{U}_{cd}^T & \mathbf{U}_{dd} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c} \\ d_0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_{x0} \\ \mathbf{P}_{y0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (9)$$

where, for example; \mathbf{U}_{cd_0} is the stiffness matrix of the \mathbf{c} coefficients obtained when minimising the total complementary energy of the system with respect to the d_0 coefficient; \mathbf{P}_{x0} and \mathbf{P}_{y0} are the constants that arise when minimising the total complementary energy with respect to \mathbf{c} and d_0 respectively; and \mathbf{c} and d_0 a vector and scalar of the unknown coefficients respectively. The solution to the problem of Equation 9 yields the coefficients of the Airy's stress function which enables the stress resultant field under the prescribed loading to be determined as per Equations 6.

2.6 Buckling

The Ritz method is used on the total potential energy to solve the buckling problem for the plate using the stress resultant distribution obtained in the pre-buckling analysis. The plate is loaded by the end-shortening Δx for pre-buckling case A and $[\Delta x, \Delta y]$ for pre-buckling case B which is increased proportionally by a loading parameter, λ .

2.6.1 Total potential energy

The total potential energy of the plate is given by the sum of the bending strain energy, U_D , transverse shear strain energy, U_H ; and external work, T , by:

$$\Pi = U_D + U_H + T, \quad (10)$$

where, for a Mindlin-Reissner laminated plate U_D , U_H and T are given by [18]:

$$\begin{aligned} U_D = & \frac{1}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \left[D_{11} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x} \right)^2 + D_{22} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2D_{12} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial y} \right) \right. \\ & + D_{66}^i \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x} \right)^2 + 2D_{16} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x} \right) \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x} \right) \\ & \left. + 2D_{26} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial y} \right) \left(2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{xz}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x} \right) \right] dy dx, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$U_{H_{ts}} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} [H_{55} \gamma_{xz}^2 + 2H_{45} \gamma_{xz} \gamma_{yz} + H_{44} \gamma_{yz}^2] dy dx \quad (12)$$

and

$$T = \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_{-a/2}^{a/2} \int_{-b/2}^{b/2} \left[N_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 + N_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 + 2N_{xy} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) \right] dy dx. \quad (13)$$

respectively. The analysis is further simplified and generalised by expressing the total potential energy in the normalised coordinate system of ξ and η (Equation 7).

2.6.2 Shape functions

The shape functions for the normalised out-of-plane displacement and transverse shear strain in the xz - and yz -directions are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} w = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N [A_{mn} X_m(x) Y_n(y)] = A_{mn} X_m Y_n, \quad \gamma_{xz} = \sum_{f=1}^F \sum_{g=1}^G [D_{fg} F_f(x) G_g(y)] = D_{fg} F_f G_g \\ \text{and} \quad \gamma_{yz} = \sum_{k=1}^{K_i} \sum_{l=1}^{L_i} [E_{kl} K_k(x) L_l(y)] = E_{kl} K_k L_l, \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

respectively, where for the w shape function, X_m and Y_n are polynomial series in the x - and y -directions respectively, M and N are the number of terms in the X_m and Y_n series respectively and A_{mn} are the unknown coefficients, for the γ_{xz} shape function, F_f and G_g are polynomial series in the x - and y -directions respectively, F and G are the number of terms in the F_f and G_g series respectively and D_{fg} the unknown coefficients and for the γ_{yz} shape function, K_k and L_l are polynomial series in the x - and y -directions respectively, K and L are the number of terms in the K_k and L_l series respectively and E_{kl} the unknown coefficients. The boundary conditions for the shape functions are implemented through selection of the polynomial series. A summary of the required shape function boundary conditions for w , γ_{xz} and γ_{yz} for given edge boundary conditions are provided in Table 1. The boundary conditions for the shape functions are implemented through circulation functions applied to Legendre polynomials [4, 8] in the form:

$$X_i(\xi) = \Gamma_x(\xi) \sum_{i=1}^I L_{i-1}(\xi) \quad \text{where} \quad \Gamma_x(\xi) = (\xi - \xi_c)^n, \quad (15)$$

where the circulation function, $\Gamma_x(\xi)$, enforces a condition at $\xi = \xi_c$ by setting $n = 0$ for a free condition, $n = 1$ for a simply-supported condition ($X_i(\xi_c) = 0$) and $n = 2$ for clamped condition ($X_i(\xi_c), \partial X_i(\xi_c)/\partial \xi = 0$). The total potential energy of the system can be expressed in terms of the unknowns A_{mn} , D_{fg} and E_{kl} by substituting the shape functions (Equation 14) into the normalised form of Equations 10-13 and performing numerical integration.

Direction	Description	Boundary condition		
		w	γ_{xz}	γ_{yz}
x -direction	Simply-supported	S-S	F-F	S-S
	Clamped	C-C	S-S	S-S
y -direction	Simply-supported	S-S	S-S	F-F
	Clamped	C-C	S-S	S-S

Table 1: Boundary conditions and corresponding shape function selection for out-of-plane deflection and transverse shear strains. S: Simply-supported; F: Free; C; Clamped; G; Guided.

2.7 Principle of stationary potential energy

Applying the principle of stationary potential energy to the non-dimensional form of the total potential energy and minimising with respect to the unknown coefficients, A_{mn} , D_{fg} and E_{kl} , results in a set of linear equations which expressed in matrix form are given by:

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K}_{AA} & \mathbf{K}_{AD} & \mathbf{K}_{AE} \\ \mathbf{K}_{AD}^T & \mathbf{K}_{DD} & \mathbf{K}_{DE} \\ \mathbf{K}_{AE}^T & \mathbf{K}_{DE}^T & \mathbf{K}_{EE} \end{bmatrix} - \lambda \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_{AA} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_{mn} \\ \mathbf{D}_{fg} \\ \mathbf{E}_{kl} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

where, for example \mathbf{K}_{AD} is the stiffness matrix of the \mathbf{A} coefficients obtained when minimising the strain energy of the system with respect to the \mathbf{D} coefficient; \mathbf{L}_{AA} the stability matrix; and \mathbf{A}_{mn} , \mathbf{D}_{fg} and \mathbf{E}_{kl} vectors of the unknown coefficients.

The solution to the eigenvalue problem of Equation 16 yields stationary points in the total potential energy which are buckling modes of the plate. The eigenvectors provide the coefficients of the out-of-plane displacement and transverse shear strain shape functions whilst the eigenvalue, λ , the load multiplier of the input uniform end-shortening.

3 Parametric studies

The parametric study is performed on a sandwich panel 1000 mm in length, 400 mm in width with an 8 mm core and 1 mm facesheets consisting of eight plies of IM7/8552 ($E_{11} = 161$ MPa, $E_{22} = 11.38$ MPa, $G_{12} = 5.17$ MPa, $\nu_{12} = 0.32$). The critical buckling load is determined for the case of uniform end-shortening with longitudinal edges free to expand and all edges simply-supported. The VS skin is achieved with a linear variation in the y -direction symmetric about the centre line of the panel in the form $[\pm\langle T_1|T_2 \rangle_2]_s$ where T_1 and T_2 are located at the edge and centre line of the panel, $[b/2, 0]$, as shown in Figure 1. Six different isotropic core core properties ($G_c = \infty, 1000, 500, 200, 100, 10$ MPa) are considered, all representing practical values ranging from high density aluminium honeycomb or syntactic foam to low density aramid honeycomb. To enable observation of the qualitative effect of core shear stiffness, the core contribution to axial and bending stiffnesses of the panel are neglected. The smeared pre-buckling stress resultant and smeared critical buckling load for every combination of angle for T_1 and T_2 from 0° to 90° , varying in 5° increments, is obtained for all core cases with normalised results provided in Figure 2. This form of plot for VS structures was first used by Olmedo and Gürdal [15] for thin plates and is useful for both quantitative and qualitative comparisons between configurations.

The panels neglecting core shear flexibility (Figure 2a) show similar buckling characteristics to the VS monolithic plates reported in Reference [1]. In both cases, the optimal straight fibre configuration is $\pm 45^\circ$, whilst the optimal VS configuration and relative improvement over the straight fibre configuration differed slightly, being 80% at $\pm\langle 15^\circ|90^\circ \rangle$ and 62% at $\pm\langle 15^\circ|85^\circ \rangle$ for the thin plate and sandwich panel respectively. Differences with Reference [1] for VS square plates are expected to be due to differences in both the structural configuration and aspect ratio. For VS plates with an aspect ratio of two, Olmedo and Gürdal [15], reported the improvement reduced to 66%.

Figure 2: Normalised critical buckling load against pre-buckling load for various sandwich core shear moduli. Thin continuous lines are for a fixed central angle, T_2 , with variable T_1 and dashed lines indicate straight fibre configurations. The critical buckling load is normalised against the maximum straight fibre configuration critical buckling load whilst the pre-buckling stiffness is normalised against the maximum straight fibre configuration pre-buckling stiffness.

Figure 3: One-dimensional sandwich panel buckling modes. Reproduced and annotated from Reference [21].

Inclusion of transverse shear effects did not significantly affect the characteristics of the normalised critical buckling load plot or relative improvement compared to straight fibre configurations for cores with a high shear modulus ($G_c = 1000, 500\text{MPa}$ in Figure 2). However, further decreasing the core shear modulus to 200MPa resulted in the normalised buckling plots in Figure 2 taking a different form with an associated reduction in improvements of VS panels compared to straight fibre configurations. The behaviour becoming more prevalent with further reductions in core shear modulus. The change in behaviour of the panels with low shear modulus cores is attributed to the critical buckling mode of the panel changing from global to core shear crimping as shown in Figures 3a and Figure 3b respectively for a one-dimensional case. Core shear crimping is a high frequency buckling mode in which displacements are predominately due to transverse shearing rather than rotation and is attributed to a low core shear modulus. The load at which crippling occurs is almost independent of skin properties being proportional to product of the core shear modulus and thickness [20]:

$$N_{\text{crimp}} \propto G_c h_c. \quad (17)$$

Crimping can often cause core material shear failure or a disbond at the skin interface and can occur in the post-buckled regime following initial global buckling. Here, large moments towards the boundary of global modes can build-up creating local peak transverse shear stresses promoting a shear crimping mode.

The behaviour and loss of performance displayed in Figure 2 for low shear modulus cores can be best explained by examining a single curve. The profile for core five ($G_c = 100\text{MPa}$) with VS $[\pm\langle T_1|45^\circ\rangle_2]_s$ skins (T_2 fixed at 45°) obtained by varying T_1 from 0° to 90° in 5° increments is provided in Figure 4b showing both the global and shear crimping buckling loads. With increasing pre-buckling stiffness, by varying T_1 from 90° towards 0° , the buckling load of the panel initially increases with critical modes being global, occurring over the full width of the panel with two to five half-waves in the x -direction. This increase in critical buckling load continues up until a maximum absolute critical buckling load of 0.710 at $\langle 30^\circ|45^\circ\rangle$, 21% higher than the best straight fibre configuration. Further decreasing T_1 beyond 30° results in an abrupt decrease in critical buckling load accompanied with a change in the buckling mode to core shear crimping occurring in localised regions towards boundary supports. Core shear crimping modes continue to occur with decreasing T_1 until a configuration of $\langle 10^\circ|45^\circ\rangle$ at which global modes again become critical. Critical buckling loads were additionally computed with ABAQUS 6.12-1 using 10mm square S4R shell elements that make use of a FSDT, the fine mesh required to achieved convergence for the high frequency shear crimping modes. Semi-analytical results were within 1% of the FEA and required significantly less degrees of freedom.

Being short in wavelength, the shear crimping modes are able to occur in localised regions of the panel and are almost unaffected by panel length or width. In the pre-buckled state the VS load redistribution, as shown in Figure 4a, creates highly loaded regions which locally exceed the critical shear crimping load, being primarily a function of core properties alone (Equation 17). This is shown by the $\langle 20^\circ|45^\circ\rangle$ mode in Figure 4b, where shear crimping occurs in a strip at the location of the highly loaded 20° fibre angles with the remainder of the panel, being below the shear crimping load, remaining unbuckled. Likewise, the $\langle 90^\circ|45^\circ\rangle$, with a 90° orientation at boundaries and 45° at the centre has a shear crimping mode occurring in the highly loaded, relative to the outer regions, central region. The maximum shear crimping buckling load in Figure 4b is achieved when the panel is loaded with a uniform stress with the straight fibre configuration of $\langle 45^\circ|45^\circ\rangle$. Here, the entire width of the panel is able to fail simultaneously in shear crimping rather

(a) Semi-analytical ($H = 10$) pre-buckling in-plane stress resultant, N_x , y -direction distribution when subject to a uniform end-shortening of $\Delta x = 1$ mm.

(b) Critical buckling load plotted for FEA with 10 mm elements and semi-analytical model (SA). FEA results provided for critical path only.

Figure 4: Low shear modulus core five, $G_c = 100$ MPa, with $\langle T_1 | 45^\circ \rangle$ VS skin.

G_c [MPa]	$[\pm\langle T_1^\circ \rangle_2]_s$		$[\pm\langle T_1^\circ T_2^\circ \rangle_2]_s$		$[\pm\langle T_1^\circ T_2^\circ T_3^\circ \rangle_2]_s$		$[\pm\langle T_1^\circ T_2^\circ T_3^\circ T_4^\circ \rangle_2]_s$	
	CP	$N_{x,crit}$	CP	$N_{x,crit}$	CP	$N_{x,crit}$	CP	$N_{x,crit}$
∞	44	0.90	13 90	1.46 (61.6%)	8 62 56	1.56 (73.4%)	1 53 57 60	1.56 (78.4%)
1000	43	0.86	13 86	1.39 (61.2%)	7 62 56	1.50 (73.7%)	1 53 56 59	1.54 (78.5%)
500	42	0.82	14 82	1.31 (60.5%)	8 61 54	1.42 (73.9%)	1 52 55 57	1.46 (78.5%)
200	39	0.71	24 57	1.01 (42.7%)	24 40 60	1.02 (42.7%)	24 32 53 50	1.03 (44.2%)
100	39	0.59	31 46	0.71 (21.1%)	31 35 53	0.72 (22.6%)	32 33 42 49	0.72 (22.7%)
10	13	0.10	4 6	0.10 (0.2%)	4 8 7	0.10 (0.3%)	2 9 7 9	0.10 (0.4%)

Table 2: Optimisation study results. Buckling loads are expressed as smeared stress resultants, $N_{x,crit}$ [kN/mm] and optimal fibre angles rounded to the nearest integer value. Number in brackets is improvement relative to optimal straight fibre (single control point) buckling load. CP: control points.

than in a local region. For core six, with a core shear modulus of 10 MPa, even the slightest load variation results in local shear crimping and the optimal VS configurations coincide with the straight fibre laminates. Above an angle of $\pm 50^\circ$ the straight fibre configurations for core six buckle in global modes and plateau at a maximum below this angle in shear crimping modes.

In all cases, the semi-analytical model used 10 terms in the pre-buckling analysis whilst for the buckling analysis a different amount of terms were used for high and low shear modulus cores due to the high frequency waves that occurred with shear crimping. For high shear modulus cores (cores one to three) 15 and 9 terms (405 degrees of freedom) were used in the x - and y -directions respectively whilst for low modulus cores (cores four to six) 20 and 15 terms (900 degrees of freedom) were used in the x - and y -directions respectively. For the FEA 4000 elements were required (20×10^3 degrees of freedom) to achieve converged results, an order of magnitude more than the semi-analytical model. An advantage of using polynomials as the shape functions is their ability to locally allow regions to exhibit high-frequency waves. Whilst it does require many terms to allow high-frequency waves to develop over the entire domain, only a small region is required to exhibit this behaviour to trigger a core shear crimping mode as shown in Figure 4b.

4 Optimisation

Using the same panel configuration as the parametric study an optimisation study was performed for all six core cases with an increasing amount of control points enabling increased tailorability for the fibre path. The optimisation procedure, implemented in MATLAB R2013a, consisted of a hybrid approach; an initial genetic algorithm (GA) followed by a interior-point algorithm starting from the GA's solution. This approach utilises the enhanced global performance of GA to identify a near-optimum solution and then switches to a faster and more efficient method for local searching. For each core, the optimum was found with variations using evenly spaced control points symmetric about $y = 0$; one control point $[\pm T_1]_{2s}$ (straight fibre configuration); two control points $[\pm\langle T_1 | T_2 \rangle_2]_s$ at $[0.50b, 0.00]$; three control points $[\pm\langle T_1 | T_2 | T_3 \rangle_2]_s$ at $[0.50b, 0.25b, 0.00]$; and four control points $[\pm\langle T_1 | T_2 | T_3 | T_4 \rangle_2]_s$ at $[0.50b, 0.33b, 0.17b, 0.00]$. A summary of the optimisation results are provided in Table 2.

Optimised solutions for one and two control points typically identified configurations very close to the parametric study results, with absolute critical buckling loads only improving by up to 2.4%, hence validating the usefulness of the coarse parametric plots particularly when considering the additional insight provided. For cores which did not suffer from crimping failure ($G_c = \infty, 1000, 500$ MPa), increasing the number of control points resulted in an improvement in buckling load, albeit to a lesser extent with each refinement, plateauing just under 80% improvement with four control points. The optimal configurations tended to distribute load towards boundaries and reduce loading in a large central region of the panel using an almost constant fibre angle with low axial stiffness. For example, the optimal four control point fibre path of the 500 MPa core was $[\pm\langle 1^\circ | 52^\circ | 55^\circ | 57^\circ \rangle_2]_s$. With increasing control points, the solutions appeared

to approach a configuration creating highly loaded axial beams along the boundaries connected by a shear web. Such configurations, however, require fibres to be steered with large in-plane fibre curvatures and thus manufacturability may be an issue.

Cores with a low shear modulus, which experience shear crimping, additionally had optimal configurations with increased loading towards boundaries. Here, the amount of redistribution, or more specifically the ratio of maximum local to smeared in-plane stress resultant was limited due to crimping modes occurring. For example, the optimal four control point fibre path of the 100MPa core was $[\pm(32^\circ|33^\circ|42^\circ|49^\circ)_2]_s$. These cores tended to reach an upper limit in improvement, over straight fibre configurations, at only two control points, with this simple linear variation seemingly being a close approximation of optimal fibre paths with additional control points. The core with a shear modulus of 10MPa found little improvement with any fibre steering due to the very low core shear flexibility promoting crippling in the presence of minor load redistributions.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, the benefits of VS sandwich panels for enhanced buckling performance were explored by allowing face-sheet laminates to have steered fibres in the transverse direction (*y*-direction). Parametric studies performed on sandwich panels with VS face-sheets indicate that the buckling performance is not only highly dependent on the fibre angle variation but additionally the core shear modulus. The buckling performance of VS sandwich panels, with respect to fibre angle variations, is similar to that of monolithic VS plates when the core shear modulus is above a threshold value. In this case, optimal fibre variations determined for VS plates additionally represent near optimal configurations for VS sandwich panels, both having similar performance gains over straight fibre configurations. However, below this threshold core shear modulus, shear crimping modes can become critical resulting in significantly reduced critical buckling loads and a reduction in improvement of straight fibre configurations. The promotion of crimping modes is due to the VS pre-buckling load redistribution creating local regions with peak in-plane stresses, significantly higher than the smeared (average) in-plane stress of the panel, locally exceeding the critical shear crimping load.

An optimisation case study was performed on uniaxially loaded sandwich panels with various core properties and fibre variations with up to four control points. Above the threshold core shear modulus, the optimal fibre paths tended to increase pre-buckling loading towards the boundaries, with angles close to 0° , and rapidly reduce loading in a large central region, with an almost constant fibre angle with low axial stiffness and good buckling performance (angles between 50° and 60°). As expected, improvements between successive increases in the number of control points reduced. For the cases considered, high shear modulus cores had improvements, over straight fibre configurations, in buckling load of 78% with four control points. Cores with a low shear modulus, on the other hand, tended to reach optimal configurations with just two control points, with increases in the number of control points having negligible improvement. Similar to high shear modulus cores, loading was increased towards panel boundaries, albeit to a much lesser extent. With reducing core shear modulus beyond the threshold value, the relative improvement in critical buckling load over straight fibre configurations achieved with VS face-sheets decreased from 78% (cores above threshold shear modulus) to less than 1%.

The smeared loads at which core shear crimping occurs for VS panels was found to be significantly lower than straight fibre cases, particularly for the VS fibre paths that are found to be optimal in panels with either high shear modulus cores or transverse shear effects neglected, e.g. thin plates. Considering the crimping modes can become critical for low shear modulus cores, reducing, or even completely eliminating, any benefit of VS, care must be taken in the design of VS sandwich panels to ensure the full potential, as available to VS monolithic plates, can be exploited.

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